

Metrics used in data analysis based on presence/absence data

- a. Frequency of occurrence (FOO)

$$\%FOO_i = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{k=1}^S l_{i,k} \times 100\%$$

S : Number of samples

$l_{i,k}$: Presence or absence of prey items i in sample k

- b. Weighted per cent of occurrence (wPOO)

$$\%wPOO_i = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{k=1}^S \frac{l_{i,k}}{\sum_{i=1}^T l_{i,k}} \times 100\%$$

T : Number of prey items

S : Number of samples

$l_{i,k}$: Presence or absence of prey items i in sample k

Reference

Deagle, B. E., Thomas, A. C., McInnes, J. C., Clarke, L. J., Vesterinen, E. J., Clare, E. L., Kartzinel, T. R., & Eveson, J. P. (2019). Counting with DNA in metabarcoding studies: How should we convert sequence reads to dietary data? *Molecular Ecology*, 28(2), 391–406. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.14734>